

Talent Readiness of PT KAI to Face the Era of Change

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ABSTRACT: PT KAI is the only rail-based transportation company in Indonesia managed by SOEs. The main services offered by PT KAI are transportation for passengers and products, while its non-core business is real estate, and its subsidiaries include six companies offering a wide range of services. PT KAI is currently undergoing changes that can be seen with the change in partnership PT KAI is moving towards Global Partnership. This can be seen by the cooperation carried out by PT KAI with other countries in carrying out the Indonesian Fast Train project. One of PT KAI's missions is to become digital-based railway transportation. This mission is a business response to changes moving into the digital era.

This research was conducted using quantitative methods. Data collection was carried out by researchers by visiting PT KAI Head Office located on Jl. Perintis Kemerdekaan No.1, Babakan Ciamis, Kec. Sumur Bandung, Bandung City, West Java, and PT KAI Training Center located in two locations, namely Jl. Kacapiring, Batununggal District, Bandung City, West Java, Indonesia, and Jl. Ir. H. Juanda No.215, Dago, Coblong District, Bandung City, West Java, Indonesian. The respondents of this study were active employees of PT KAI totaling 168 respondents. The method of data collection is carried out by du event, namely Quick Count or Pooling Priority, and also through Questionnaires. The data processed then was from 140 respondents. The data reduction was carried out because it was found that there were outliers of 28 respondents or 16.67% obtained through examination with the SPSS 26 tool with the Casewise Diagnostic method.

Researchers also provide solutions to change issues so that PT KAI is better prepared to face the era of change in the future, consist of PT KAI Goes International through English Habits, and Work Abroad Opportunities for PT KAI's Top Talent, Transforming Service Quality and Security by maximizing the use of AI and Renewable Technology in all Business processes, Creating Synergies (Including SOEs) through harmonious and collaborative strategic alliances with other state-owned companies, Global Partnership as the best transportation ecosystem solution for Indonesia by opening up to the existence of a Global partnership business scheme.

KEYWORDS: Culture, Leaders, Digital, Organizational Capabilities, Service, Talent Readiness.

INTRODUCTION

A company that wants to progress and develop will definitely experience many changes both from outside influences, and from within. The change itself can occur either with the use of technology (tools, programs, applications), changes in the way of working, changes in working hours, changes in reporting systems, changes in colleagues, changes in authority, new workloads, new partners, business models, and so on. One of the major changes that has occurred and seen an impact on every line of industry is the presence of the Covid-19 Pandemic. The pandemic has made many things change both systematically and people's habits. The Covid-19 pandemic has changed operational methods, technology, structure, culture, human resource management, and talent management across business lines. This is driven by these new developments to better prepare for the future, digital-related era. From hiring new employees to ending, most human resource management procedures were done online during the pandemic. This encourages the development of the post-pandemic period because the procedures are more effective, fast, accurate, and credible.

Therefore, companies need to realize the importance of readiness for change, because change itself is dynamic and can occur either sooner or later. Companies that are aware of resilience to uncertain situations of change, have all the prerequisites to face future possibilities [1]. This situation is known as VUCA (Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, and Ambiguity). The investigation found that measures taken by many authorities to contain the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic, including travel restrictions, quarantine measures, and border closures, have resulted in many affected parties [2]. This also has an impact on PT KAI as the only train service operator in Indonesia.

At a time when change is the rule rather than the exception, an organization's ability to be flexible has become paramount. Readiness to change is essential for change to be implemented successfully [3, 4]. When readiness exists, organizations are ready to embrace

change and resistance can be reduced. When the opposite happens, the change can be rejected. Work engagement is seen as a workplace approach designed to ensure that employees are committed to the organization's goals and values, motivated to contribute to the success of the organization and simultaneously to enhance their own sense of well-being [5].

PT KAI as the only business operating in the Indonesian railway transportation sector is also experiencing changes. The industrial revolution has resulted in advanced economic growth, increased productivity, and prosperity in countries that have managed to reap most of its positive impacts, including in the railway industry. The existence of this industrial revolution has also changed the railway industry which has begun to switch to digital-based transportation, where this is also one of PT KAI's missions that is to provide a safe, efficient, digital-based, and rapidly growing transportation system to meet customer needs [6]. One of PT KAI's missions is also one of the drivers of change that occurs at PT KAI. Another change can also be seen in terms of the partnership carried out by PT KAI at this time. With the existence of PT KCIC (Kereta Cepat Indonesia China), PT KAI's partnership has begun to move towards global partnership [7]. Based on initial interviews conducted by researchers, information was obtained that the high-speed train currently under construction is not only from Jakarta to Bandung, but the farthest route of this project is Jakarta to Surabaya.

With the existence of global partnerships plus the increasingly rapid digital era, researchers believe that there will be many demands from stakeholders, both the public and the Indonesian government, against PT KAI. Along with these demands and changes, PT Kai needs to focus more on readiness in the era of change. It is undeniable that with the dream to become a transportation industry that can reach all corners of Indonesia from Sabang to Merauke, in the future there will be many big projects waiting for PT KAI and it is certain that more global partnerships will be carried out by PT KAI in the future. Therefore, readiness to face the era of change is relevant and plays an important role for PT KAI's business progress and to prepare for turbulence and uncertain disruptions in the future

BUSINESS ISSUE

Based on initial interviews conducted by researchers with Vice President Training Management, Manager of Training Center PT KAI Dago, Specialist of Career Management PT KAI, and Manager of Talent Management PT KAI, researchers found five main aspects that became factors of PT KAI in preparing and facing the era of change, namely Culture, Leaders, Digital, Service, and Organizational Capabilities. Specialist of Career Management and Manager of Talent Management added that in addition to these five aspects, there is one supporting factor that is an important thing that must be considered, namely the management of talents at PT KAI so that they are able to understand and participate in preparing themselves to face the era of change. These aspects are then processed by researchers using Ishikawa Diagram (Fish-Bone) to analyze the root cause problem for the creation of a conceptual framework which will be mentioned below. The following is the Fish Bone Diagram Readiness for Change in PTKAI:

Figure 1. Fish Bone Diagram of PT KAI's Readiness for Change (Source: Author's Processed Data, 2023)

Businesses today face unprecedented challenges operating in an increasingly unstable, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous global environment (VUCA). Leaders are also faced with increasing competition, globalization, increasing demand for social responsibility, and the current technological revolution causing disruptions in the marketplace. Therefore, leaders need to challenge their mental models in their efforts to build and maintain high-performance organizations [3]. At the core of the challenges facing companies today is learning how to manage talent in situations of growing volatility and uncertainty in the global business environment, allied to the need to deal with new scales, complexities, and organizational forms following developments and changes [4].

VUCA is one of the drivers of change both in small and large scales, and this uncertainty and change will certainly intersect with the interests of stakeholders, namely business owner shareholders, employee and management, customer community, and regulators and associations. Therefore, researchers create a matrix that shows each VUCA element (Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, and Ambiguity) to each stakeholder to find out the analysis of business situations to face future challenges as in the table below:

Table 1. VUCA Business Situation Analysis

VUCA Business Situation Analysis	Stakeholders Involved			
	Business Owners and Shareholders	Employees and Management	Customer and Community	Regulator and Association
<p>Volatility Things change, but we don't know how they change and how to be ready to face them.</p>	It's difficult to anticipate business certainty due to changes in business behavior after the pandemic moved into the digital age. TM is a consideration for business owners to anticipate this volatility situation.	Employees and management are forced to prepare quickly because of sudden changes, due to the faster digital wave due to the pandemic. TM is the cornerstone of managing and employees facing this volatility.	Customers are forced to follow the digitization process in the process of purchasing and using PT KAI products and services. Customers demand service from talented people.	Regulators will adjust regulations due to sudden changes post-pandemic, driven by digital technology. Provide assurance and balance for talented people to feel safe in volatile situations.
<p>Uncertainty Changes are unexpected, and the duration cannot be predicted</p>	The owner must prepare a capital reserve because at any time, changes may occur. The need for investment for talent development will increase so that the company becomes relevant after the pandemic	The emergence of management awareness to always improve digital mindset and digital readiness in the face of uncertainty.	Communities are getting smarter, as information becomes more transparent and informative driven by digital technologies.	Regulation anticipates the emergence of sudden changes driven by technological changes. The association adjusts regulations regarding the importance of talent management to respond to situations of uncertainty.
<p>Complexity There are many interacting factors and drivers</p>	The owner considers many factors in decision making, because of the various variables that affect the business situation facing a new era. Shareholders support owner decisions in the development of talent management.	Management considers the many variables that affect business and employee performance due to just passing the pandemic phase facing the digital era. Digital readiness of talented employees must be responded to quickly.	Customers have a large selection of alternatives of the products and services needed, adjusting to the complexity of the offer from the industry. The number of these offers occurs because of the creativity of talented human capital.	The association considers the interests of regulators and industry to be able to get out of the complexity of business in the digital era.
<p>Ambiguity Cause-effect relationships are unclear, there are no precedents or previous experience to fall back on</p>	Business Owners predict the consequences that arise suddenly, which has an impact on indecision in decision making. Talent management in decision making mitigates ambiguity.	Management maximizes digitalization in managing talent management, for the efficiency of business operations.	Customers are hesitant to get a service because there are so many offers through digital media.	Regulations are changing rapidly, to adapt to rapidly changing causal factors.

(Source: Author's Processed Data, 2023)

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In accordance with the root cause analysis found by the researcher through the initial interview, the researcher read journals related to each aspect to create a conceptual framework used in this study. The purpose of this framework is to help researchers get an in-depth analysis and get the right answers to answer research questions.

This framework will examine the readiness of PT KAI where there are 5 aspects that influence, namely culture, leaders, digital, service, and organizational capabilities. Talent Readiness theory is adopted from several past researchers [8, 9, 10, 11], Cultural literacy is obtained from Greet Hofstede with national cultural theory where there are 5 dimensions, namely power distance, individualism, masculinity, long-term orientation and uncertainty avoidance [12, 13]. The leader aspect consists of 4 dimensions, namely empowerment, inspiration, leading change, and shared vision. This theory was adopted from the theory of leadership models [14, 15, 16, 17, 18].

The third aspect is digital where there are two dimensions, namely digital mastery and learning agility [19, 20]. The next aspect is service with RATER theory by Parasuraman where there are 5 influential dimensions, namely tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy [21, 22, 23]. The latter is the aspect of organizational capabilities. This theory was adopted from the book Organizational Behavior written by Yuni Ros Bangun. In this aspect, there are 9 dimensions, namely speed, innovation, customer connectivity, adaptable to change, strategic responsiveness, international environment, ready to strategic alliance, efficiency, and talent [24].

HYPOTHESIS

The hypotheses in this study are as follows:

1. H1: Aspects of Culture, Leaders, Digital, Service, and Organizational Capabilities have a simultaneous influence on Talent Readiness.
2. H2: Aspects of Culture, Leaders, Digital, Service, and Organizational Capabilities have a partial influence on Talent Readiness.
3. H3: The aspect that has the most dominant influence is Leaders and the second most dominant is Service, the temporary conclusion in this hypothesis is that Leaders who have the character of serving are aspects that have the most significant influence on Talent Readiness at PT KAI

Figure 3. Hypothesis Analysis
(Source: Author Processed Data Through Pooling Priority, 2023)

METHODOLOGY

This study used a quantitative approach. The quantitative approach requires the collection, evaluation, interpretation, and documentation of study data. To identify samples and populations, determine investigation strategies, collect and analyze data, present results, make interpretations, and write research in a manner consistent with surveys or experimental studies, there are specific methods applicable to surveys and experimental research. [25].

To derive hypothesis, researchers asked respondents to rank aspects that affect talent readiness and sort each dimension for each aspect by doing priority pooling or quick count. This is used by researchers to obtain provisional conclusions which will later be confirmed through quantitative analysis. To obtain the appropriate number of respondents, researchers visited PT KAI Head Office located on Jl. Perintis Kemerdekaan No.1, Babakan Ciamis, Kec. Sumur Bandung, Kota Bandung, Jawa Barat, and PT KAI Training Center located in two locations, namely Jl. Kacapiring, Kecamatan Batununggal, Kota Bandung, Jawa Barat, Indonesia, and Jl. Ir. H. Juanda No.215, Dago, Kecamatan Coblong, Kota Bandung, Jawa Barat, Indonesia.

More comprehensive quantitative data were taken through questionnaires. The questionnaire can be accessed by prospective respondents through a barcode that has been provided on the sheet used to collect or rank the influence of each dimension on the variable and each variable on the objective. In the questionnaire, there are 5 aspects according to the conceptual framework, namely culture, leaders, digital, service, and organizational capabilities. Each aspect is formed by several dimensions. Each dimension has 2 questionnaire questions with options 1-6 where 1 strongly disagrees, 2 disagrees, 3 tends to disagree, 4 tends to agree, 5 agrees, and 6 strongly agrees. The purpose of quantitative methods is to test provisional conclusions.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

From the 212 questionnaires distributed, there were 168 respondents that gave questionnaire responses. From the initial 168 respondents, researchers found an anomaly, where after conducting a Normality Test, it was known that the data was not distributed normally. This result is known by performing the Kolmogorov-Smirnov One-Sample Test where the significance is below 0.05 which means the data is not normally distributed. The data can be sorted from the image below:

Table 2. First Normality Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		168
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	2.47725529
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.123
	Positive	.106
	Negative	-.123
Test Statistic		.123
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000 ^c

(Source: Author Processed Data, Using SPSS Tools, 2023)

Data cleansing is needed to increase the validity and reliability of data to obtain good quality information to obtain relevant processed results in making conclusions. In this case, SPSS through the Casewise Diagnostic menu detected 28 respondents out of 168 (16.67%) or one in six respondents filled out an outlier questionnaire, so that the processed and quality data left 140 respondents. Outliers are data that have characteristics that differ greatly from other observations and appear in the form of extreme values for either single variables or combination variables. Below is the data discarded in accordance with the recommendations of the SPSS tool:

Table 3. Casewise Diagnostic

Casewise Diagnostics^a

Case Number	Std. Residual	TOTAL_Y	Predicted Value	Residual	Case Number	Std. Residual	TOTAL_Y	Predicted Value	Residual
5	-2.246	20	25.67	-5.669	107	-7.067	5	22.84	-17.839
12	-1.050	19	21.65	-2.651	116	1.695	28	23.72	4.277
14	3.590	30	20.94	9.063	121	1.300	30	26.72	3.282
16	-1.535	20	23.88	-3.876	124	3.008	26	18.41	7.594
35	-1.815	25	29.58	-4.581	127	-1.528	22	25.86	-3.856
36	-2.235	15	20.64	-5.641	132	1.465	30	26.30	3.699
49	-1.183	26	28.98	-2.985	136	1.038	30	27.38	2.620
52	-1.564	25	28.95	-3.947	138	-1.955	19	23.93	-4.934
54	-1.119	20	22.82	-2.824	142	1.249	27	23.85	3.152
58	1.857	30	25.31	4.688	153	1.488	27	23.24	3.757
78	1.076	30	27.29	2.715	159	-1.922	20	24.85	-4.851
81	-1.053	25	27.66	-2.658	163	-2.098	19	24.30	-5.297
82	-1.218	26	29.08	-3.075	165	-1.019	18	20.57	-2.571
83	-1.055	27	29.66	-2.663	168	-1.182	23	25.98	-2.984

(Source: Author Processed Data, Using SPSS Tools, 2023)

After exposing 28 data, 140 of the best and quality data are left, which is expected to provide in-depth analysis. The Figure 4 on the left, shows histogram of 168 data with outliers as it could be seen with a very wide spread of data. And the Figure 4 on the right, shows histogram of 140 respondents with the good spreading of data and become the high-quality data to be analyze.

Figure 4. Histogram Comparison of 168 Data with 28 Outliers, and 140 High Quality Data Source: Author Processed Data, Using SPSS Tools, 2023

Data in this research was obtained through two data collection methods, namely through quick count or pooling priority and also through questionnaire data processed using SPSS 26 Tools. Data obtained through priority pooling / quick count is used to analyze hypotheses, while data from SPSS quick count is used to test the hypotheses obtained.

After conducting the Validity Test, Reliability Test, and Classical Assumption Test (Normality Test, Multicollinearity Test, and Heteroskedasticity Test), the researcher conducted a hypothesis test using the SPSS 26 tool, the results of which are as shown in the table below:

Table 4. ANOVA Table

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1182,972	5	236,594	167,745	.000 ^b
	Residual	188,999	134	1,410		
	Total	1371,971	139			

a. Dependent Variable: TOTAL_Y
 b. Predictors: (Constant), TOTAL_X5, TOTAL_X1,

(Source: Author Processed Data, Using SPSS Tools, 2023)

The ANOVA table with a significance value of F below 0.05 which means five variables (culture, leaders, digital, service, and organizational capabilities), simultaneously affect the output, i.e., talent readiness

Table 5. Significance of each variable Partially (Source: SPSS 26, 2023)

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	-2,963	1,240		-2,390	0,018	-5,415	-0,511
	TOTAL_X 1	0,056	0,021	0,098	2,669	0,009	0,014	0,097
	TOTAL_X 2	-0,082	0,035	-0,109	-2,313	0,022	-0,152	-0,012
	TOTAL_X 3	0,218	0,062	0,180	3,516	0,001	0,095	0,341
	TOTAL_X 4	0,212	0,032	0,352	6,663	0,000	0,149	0,276
	TOTAL_X 5	0,154	0,017	0,515	9,106	0,000	0,120	0,187

While table 3 shows whether each variable, individually or partially has significance or influence on talent readiness. This can be seen in the section (Sig.), each variable has a significance value below 0.05. Through this table, it can be seen that the five variables have a partial significant influence on output or talent readiness.

A. Analysis Descriptive of Hypothesis

1. H1: Aspects of Culture, Leaders, Digital, Service, and Organizational Capabilities have a simultaneous influence on Talent Readiness.

Looking at table 4, ANOVA Table Analysis, shows a significance value below 0.05 indicating that Organizational Culture, Leaders, Digital, Services, and Capabilities influence simultaneously or simultaneously on Talent Readiness.

2. H2: Aspects of Culture, Leaders, Digital, Service, and Organizational Capabilities have a partial influence on Talent Readiness. In accordance with Table 5, Multiple Regression Analysis, each variable has a significance below 0.05, where the table shows that Culture has a significance value of 0.009, Leader has a significance value of 0.022, Digital has a significance value of 0.00056, Services has a significance value of 0.0000000000000064 and Organizational Capability has a significance value of 0.000000000000000011. Each variable has a significance value below 0.05 indicating that each variable has a partial influence on Talent Readiness.

3. H3: The aspect that has the most dominant influence is Leaders and the second most dominant is Service, the temporary conclusion in this hypothesis is that Leaders who have the character of serving are aspects that have the most significant influence on Talent Readiness at PT KAI

The results of the Multiple Regression Linear Analysis Method, give different answers. It can be seen that the one with the smallest significance value, or the most significant is the Organizational Capability with a significance value of 0.00000000000000000011, and the Service is the second most significant with a significance value of 0.000000000000064.

Based on these results, Service still has a significant influence on Talent Readiness, just like the results of Priority Pooling. However, there is a difference where in priority pooling, the Leader becomes one of the most significant while the results of the Analysis using the Multiple Regression Linear method provide the answer that the Organizational Capability becomes a significant one as well.

Through these two results, researchers found that there is a People and Process which is an important thing that affects Talent Readiness at PT KAI. Servant Leader is PT KAI's answer to prepare Talent Readiness to face changes in the future. This result is obtained from the results of priority pooling before the questionnaire is distributed. Leadership style with the concept of servant leadership, is the answer for PT KAI to be ready to face changes in the future.

Servant leadership builds organizational capabilities from all dimensions in this variable. Servant Leaders will be able to innovate to prepare talent readiness. To create fast service and with good customer connectivity, the role of servant leaders is to build a climate that is expected to influence every person at PT KAI to provide the best service to customers in order to establish the best possible relationship and connectivity with customers.

With PT KAI's partnership seen with other countries in the development of Indonesia's railway infrastructure, it is necessary to have leaders who have strategic concepts that are responsive and ready for strategic alliances. Servant leaders will care about the talents in PT KAI and prepare everyone to adapt to changes that occur in the future either with the changes in partnership mentioned above, or due to unknown turbulence.

BUSINESS SOLUTION

Figure 5. Predictors Determination (Source: Author Processed Data, 2023)

The predictors in this study were based on two data analysis methods, namely quick calculations based on pooling and processed data using SPSS 26. Predictors using quick counts serve to test and establish the hypothesis of this study. While analysis using the SPSS, method is used to test and validate hypotheses that have been set.

The two most dominant predictors according to Quick Count/Pooling are Leaders with a weight of 0.38 and Service with a weight of 0.21. While the most dominant based on multiple linear regression methods using SPSS tools are Organizational Capability with a weight of 0.515 and Service with a weight of 0.352. Interestingly from these two predictor determinations, the service variable was consistent as the dominant factor. Through these two methods, three predictors with the highest weight were found, namely Organizational Ability, Service, and Leaders, which need to be considered in preparing PT KAI's talents to face the era of change.

A. Organizational Capabilities and Service

The ability of SPSS-based organizations that are processed is the most important variable in preparing PT KAI's talents to face the era of change. Through the *APPENDIX* regarding Matrix Analysis and the Conclusion Matrix Analysis table, there are several things that need to be considered by PT KAI to be a solution to prepare PT KAI's talents to face changes, which are as follows:

1. Focus activities and resources to improve Organizational Capabilities on the variable dimensions of the International Environment (X5.12, X5.11), and improve Services on the dimensions of Responsiveness (X4.5, X4.6), Reliability (X4. 3, X4.4), Tangibles (X4.1, X4.2), Empathy (X4.9, X4.10), Assurance (X4.7, X4.8).

a. International Environment

In question X5.12 regarding English mastery, there is a low score. PT KAI, which has started a global partnership, needs to create an English-speaking climate in daily work activities, this can be started with a compulsory English day for all PT KAI talents to be able to familiarize themselves and force employees to learn English. English as an international compulsory language needs to be mastered by PT KAI talents to face the Global Partnership. In addition, it is necessary for employees who have High Potential and High-Performance talents in PT KAI, given the opportunity to work abroad in order to have global business insight to face global partnerships carried out by PT KAI, and do not rule out the possibility, PT KAI can do business abroad. This is also an activity to answer the X5.11 statement which speaks of the knowledge of world-class railway companies.

b. Responsiveness

In the responsiveness dimension in statements X4.5 and X4.6 related to quick responsiveness to serve customers and quick and accurate responses to customer complaints, PT KAI needs to instil a culture of discipline so that employees respond quickly not only to problems at work but to small problems in general. This activity is carried out to avoid silos at PT KAI, so that responsiveness itself is not only applied to customers, but to improve a responsive work climate, increase a high sense of ownership, so that all PT KAI talents have harmony and rhythm together to face the era of change.

c. Reliability

Statements X4.3 and X4.4, talk about trains in Indonesia are adequate for customers and well maintained, as well as the reliability of PT KAI as the only rail-based transportation service in Indonesia. Here, PT KAI needs to pay attention to all aspects of the railway by carrying out routine maintenance on all Trains, Security and Comfort both on the train, to every station in Indonesia, also pay attention to infrastructure facilities including railway lines (rails, roads and bridges), as well as train signalling for safety. This activity needs to be considered by PT KAI to be ready to face changes with quality infrastructure, international standards. In the signalling section, according to the results of an interview with PT KAI leaders, it was found that PT KAI is currently developing digital signalling, anticipating the LRT and Indonesian Fast Train business.

d. Tangibles

The tangibles dimension in the service variable with statements X4.1 and X4.2 discusses the Products and Services provided by PT KAI to customers. The focus of activities here is to improve customer experience. For this reason, PT KAI here needs to innovate so that there is an impression that is easy for customers to remember, thus creating a memorable customer experience starting from physical and non-physical access. For example, getting ticket services by visiting the counter where customers can feel comfortable queuing a little, air conditioning, friendly and very helpful waiters, safe and comfortable waiting rooms, and so on. For non-physical customers, customers should find it easy to book tickets, reschedule tickets, cancel tickets, and complain online. PT KAI here must provide a Chatbots which must later be responded directly by PT KAI employees so that customers can reach PT KAI easily, quickly, and easily.

e. Empathy

This dimension (X4.9 and X4.10) discusses the attention of PT KAI employees to customers with clear communication and very helpful customers. Here PT KAI needs to instill a hospitality climate to all its employees. This can be done by PT KAI by instilling the obligation to greet each other between employees when passing by in the office, and the obligation to greet customers at stations and trains, as well as increasing awareness of all talents to be able to see and feel whether there are customers who need help from PT KAI employees. In facing changes in entering global business with the global partnership carried out by PT KAI, talents need to pay attention to changes in customer behavior globally. This can be done by PT KAI by providing special training by providing international customer case studies, conducting international customer research, and benchmarking consumer behavior in international railway companies, to create empathy business sense for every talent at PT KAI.

f. Assurance

X4.7 and X4.8 in the variable service, assurance dimension discusses customer expectations of PT KAI. The statement in it is here we believe passengers in Indonesia prefer to use train services compared to other public transportation, and we believe PT KAI's operations (time and ease of access) are in line with customer expectations. PT KAI here needs to expand the range of train destinations at prices that must be cheaper than airplanes. With this issue, through interviews conducted by researchers, the Indonesian Fast Train is targeted not only Jakarta-Bandung, but also to Surabaya. It was a testament to the expansion of the range of quality railways and competed with aircraft services. To respond to future changes, PT KAI must guarantee customer needs so that global partners will be more interested, because the large population in Indonesia is a broad market for Global Partner investment. This is where talents need to be ready to face new business and new reach of PT KAI.

2. Maintaining Quality and Efficiency to improve variables Organizational Capability in the variable dimensions Speed (X5.1, X5.2), Adapting to Change (X5.7, X5.8), Innovation (X5.3, X5.4), Efficiency (X5.15, X5.16), Strategic Responsiveness (X5.9, X5.10), Customer Connectivity (X5.5, X5.6), Ready for Strategic Alliances (X5.13, X5.14), and Talent (X5.17, X5.18).

a. Speed

The speed dimension here discusses the speed of change response with creative thinking in finding solutions. PT KAI here can take advantage of digitalization to improve high-speed business services and activities. PT KAI needs to benchmark reputable international train operators so as not to be left behind and be able to match PT KAI's growth pace to face changes in the future.

b. Adaptable to Change

In this dimension, the concern is adaptation to the changing environment and work processes as well as awareness of the changes themselves. In this case, PT KAI needs to improve the quality of the organization that quickly adapts to changes, especially those triggered by global partnerships and the desire to become digital based railway transportation. PT KAI needs to emphasize the work climate and culture of AKHLAK (Amanah, Kompeten, Harmonis, Loyal, Adaptif, and Kolaboratif) BUMN.

c. Innovation

Innovation programs and planning in all process lines are one of the important things in variable organizational capabilities. PT KAI's talents need to be placed also as a group of innovators who work agilely like Start Up. PT KAI here can conduct innovation competitions between PT KAI talents, and it is also closed to open innovation and crowdsourcing by holding competitions also to external parties where anyone can participate, and the results of this can be developed by PT KAI to become a project or new innovation development program at PT KAI. Maximizing the use of artificial intelligence and renewable technology is also inevitable by PT KAI to face changes where PT KAI's talents must be prepared to face it.

d. Efficiency

In this dimension, discussing efficiency as a business process motto and the efficiency of PT KAI's talents doing their respective jobs. Here, PT KAI must instill breakthroughs that are low-cost high impact, so that the focus of quality and the spirit of efficiency are maintained. PT KAI must continue to innovate both in terms of service, product, and process, through technology as a driver of change.

e. Strategic Responsiveness

Strategic responsiveness is a driver that is able to create a system to provide strategic responses in the face of turbulence and external disturbances, in order to create policies in the face of change. In this case, PT KAI needs to carry out strategic steps and policies, including strategic corporate actions such as global partnerships that are being carried out and developed by PT KAI. The experience of overseas operators facing turbulence can be used as a lesson for PT KAI.

f. Customer Connectivity

In this dimension, the questionnaire statement discusses the maintenance of connectivity with PT KAI stakeholders and intimacy. In this case, PT KAI again profiles customer data, then segments which ones are priorities, based on frequency, ticket purchases with high spending power, where valuable customers will be found. Connectivity is carried out through gathering programs that can be done in special train cars for valuable customers, which are packed with Tourism, as well as to increase Indonesian tourism. Here, PT KAI is ready to change focusing on customers, especially valuable customers with special programs designed in such a way, which of course can improve corporate brands both domestically and abroad. Through this, Customer Intimacy and operation excellence as indicators can continue to increase.

g. Ready to Strategic Alliance

Partnership strategy is something that needs to be considered for the sustainability of PT KAI's business growth and it needs to be believed that strategic alliances are important and indispensable. Seeing the condition that the railway business is capital intensive, then, the choice of Ready to Strategic Alliance with overseas partnerships as strategic partners is a necessity to meet business capital so as not to interfere with the State Budget. The development of trains with the discovery of Fast Trains, Artificial Intelligence, Digitalization Systems, Security and Comfort, can be the choice of customers who can compete with aircraft services.

h. Talent

Talent becomes a major part in a company. Top talent at PT KAI is expected to be on par with world class railway company talent. In addition, talent competence must also compete with global railway talent. In this case, PT KAI needs to carry out a talent management process both from recruitment (both internally and externally) by conducting talent identification. Talented people must be collected in a container, namely the talent pool. After being in the talent pool, then this best talent must be developed to prepare these talents to be able to influence their colleagues to be ready to face changes in the future. In addition, they also need to be prepared in the succession plan program in order to become future leaders.

B. Leaders

Leaders are a concern in the discussion in this business solution, because the discovery of leaders to be the most dominant predictor affects obtained by the pooling method. The pooling method is carried out when explaining the conceptual talent readiness framework which is influenced by the 5 variables of this study as previously explained. Through this pooling, respondents fill in which rank has the highest effect on talent readiness. The results of the pooling showed that the highest ranking was influenced by leaders who were 38% (64 people from 168 respondents). This is interesting and needs to be considered because the respondents' conscience shows that leaders have the highest influence compared to culture, digital, service, and organizational capabilities in preparing PT KAI's talents to face change. And this is also in line with the slogan "The Man Behind the Gun" which was also confirmed by senior leaders through interviews conducted by researchers.

a. Empowerment

Empowerment in this study is where leaders expect talent to provide the best ideas and leadership prioritizes empowering team members in achieving maximum team success. Talent empowerment is one of the important things that PT KAI needs to pay attention to in obtaining success in facing change. When talent feels included, they will give the best performance in their work. Talent needs to be prepared and involved in facing the era of change so that there is no gap in readiness to face changes in the future.

b. Inspiring

Inspiring in this research discusses leaders who become role models at work and leaders who are able to express positive things to inspire team members. To prepare talents to face the era of change, PT KAI must have leaders and top management who are able to inspire by challenging young people as successors or succession of leadership. Talents will be better prepared to face future challenges when challenged by leaders and involved in risky decision making, to increase insight and critical thinking of talents facing challenges and the era of change in the future.

c. Lead Change

PT KAI's Senior Leaders and Top Management need to teach sensitivity to every talent in PT KAI regarding changes that affect and give progress to PT KAI. Therefore, every talent needs to be responsive to the challenges and opportunities for the progress of PT KAI. In this case, PT KAI's leaders lead holistic changes from the center to the regions in all lines of the organization that are in rhythm and have harmony.

d. Shared Vision

Shared Vision is important to face the era of change because it will accelerate adaptation to the change itself so that policy responses related to changes in the future are easy to anticipate and also to encourage the involvement of everyone in the organization. PT KAI needs to have a clear vision and mission and can be passed down to every department division in it. Leaders here must be able to communicate the vision and mission of the future to the entire team well to motivate and provide challenges for the progress of PT KAI, as well as prepare talents to face change.

IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

The Implementation Plan in this study focuses on what has been formulated in the business solution. The approach uses the concept of 5W1H (What, Why, Where, Who, When, and How), so in detail it can be written as follows:

A. *PT KAI Goes International*

What (1) : English Habits

Why: With the start of the global partnership carried out by PT KAI currently on the Indonesian Fast Train project, it is possible that more global partners will be interested in working with PT KAI. PT KAI must prepare cross-border mixed talent as a consequence of global partnerships. Therefore, existing talents must be prepared to keep pace with PT KAI's external global talents, and must even be able to become team leaders in the global talent collaboration.

Where: At the strategic level, starting from the corporate level, to the business level.

Who: Starting from employees who have just entered as change agents and employees who are prepared in the talent pool to influence all divisions and business lines.

When: Overall, the English-speaking climate is made once a week, but for senior leaders, it can be done at business meetings starting with bilingual meetings to familiarize English-speaking talents.

How: Create binding policies issued by the president director. Make English language training not in the classroom but on the job, with the concept of coaching mentoring from internal. For example, leaders with good and qualified English skills become coaches and mentors to discuss English, building a climate in their environment based on the policies of the directors. And this is one of the performance indicators of leaders who become coaches / mentors.

What (2): Work abroad opportunities

Why: To accelerate the talent development process, as well as adapt the experience of business changes both internal and external that have been experienced by global railway companies.

Where: Overseas, other countries that partner with PT KAI Who: Top Talents

When: After cooperation with global companies

How: Embedding an agreement that allows top talent to work contractually for PT KAI's global partner company. To get top talent who has the capability to participate in this program, a very strict selection is needed to meet global standards. Top talents are sent not to learn but to work in global companies to adapt science and technology from outside. This is a process of transferring knowledge and technology quickly and relevantly. Top talents who are given this opportunity must be given a target to innovate and share knowledge when they have finished participating in the program.

B. *Transforming Service Quality and Security*

What: Maximizing the use of AI and Renewable Technology in all Business processes

Why: In this finding, either by pooling or processed SPSS, service is the key to the sustainability of industries engaged in services such as PT KAI as the only rail-based transportation industry in Indonesia. Therefore, services need to be transformed to be safer, more comfortable, healthier, and of higher quality. The use of digitalization and artificial intelligence is the entrance to service transformation to face the era of change triggered by customer demanding.

Where: Starting from the Indonesian Fast Train which will operate

Who: Involving start-ups engaged in digital technology and digital services. When: As Soon As Possible, because the digital era is in sight.

How: Through market research, continuous innovation in improvement (Continuous Improvement), Benchmarking through top

talent working abroad.

C. Creating Synergies (Including BUMN)

What (1) : Harmonious and Collaborative Strategic Alliance with BUMN.

Why: With the aim of sharing resources both funds, competencies, knowledge, and technology so that it is more productive and efficient, and relatively easier to control, because in one BUMN family. In addition, this synergy activity will improve the nation's economy.

Where: Forum BUMN

Who: PT KAI's Decision Makers and Top Talent as a succession plan.

When: It has been started through the BUMN synergy forum. Here PT KAI must be more involved and leader in the transportation business.

How: Initiating and proposing joint projects as a solution from PT KAI to respond to changes by involving top talents in the synergy of BUMN.

What (2): Strengthening The Culture of AKHLAK BUMN

Why: The concept is good, Top-Down from BUMN and tested and implementation can be compared by BUMN. This needs to be done because AKHLAK is mandatory from the Minister of BUMN.

Where: All business lines of PT KAI from employees, outsourcing, to touching partners to be in tune with challenges and changes in the future.

Who: Top Leaders must be role models for the implementation of BUMN AKHLAK Culture and must be continuously instilled in all PT KAI talents so that they become DNA and ingrained in running PT KAI's business.

When: It has been started through the SOE synergy forum. Here PT KAI must be more involved and leader in the transportation business.

How: Encouragement from role models is continuously carried out. Reward and Punishment in a transparent and soft approach. This is done in order to realize sustainable business performance and consistently grow and develop.

D. Global Partnership as The Best Transportation Ecosystem Solution for Indonesia

What: Open up to the existence of a Global partnership business scheme.

Why: To be the best transportation ecosystem solution for Indonesia, PT KAI cannot move alone. Funds that are too large for the state budget are also not the best solution. Partnership Global, is one of the alternative choices to realize PT KAI as the best transportation ecosystem solution for Indonesia. The size of the Indonesian market with the 4th largest population in the world is a magnet for outside companies to cooperate and invest in Indonesia.

Where: Starting from the railway ecosystem on the island of Java, followed by expansion to other islands. Who: PT KAI partners with reputable foreign railway companies.

When: After PT KAI went public.

How: Revamping yourself towards an IPO. With an IPO, PT KAI will find it easier to get capital from the domestic and foreign public. With PT KAI's IPO, it will increase the interest of investors both domestically and abroad to invest in PT KAI.

CONCLUSION AND RECCOMENDATION

A. Conclusion

- a. Global Partnership and Digital Era are issues faced by PT KAI facing the era of change.
- b. Data collection is carried out by quick count (pooling priority), and questionnaires. Of the 168 respondents, 28 data outliers were found (1 in 6 people did not actually fill out the questionnaire). Finally, the data is processed through SPSS totalling 140 data.
- c. Variable Culture, Leaders, Digital, Service, and Organizational Capabilities simultaneously affect talent readiness at PT KAI. This was found from the results of SPSS data processing with a significance of F value below 0.05.
- d. Variable Culture, Leaders, Digital, Service, and Organizational Capabilities have a partial effect on talent readiness at PT KAI. This was found from the results of processing SPSS data through multiple linear regression methods, and was characterized by the significance value of each variable below 0.05.

- e. A predictor was found based on the quick count (pooling priority) method where Leaders became the most dominant variable with a weight value of 0.38 and Service became the second most dominant with a weight of 0.21.
- f. Predictors were found based on the results of SPSS data processing where Organizational Capabilities became the first most dominant variable with a weight value of 0.515, and Service became the second most dominant with a weight of 0.352.
- g. Through these two methods, 3 predictors were found in this study, namely, Leaders, Service, and Organizational Capabilities. Service through these two methods, consistent as a dominant predictor means, Service is an important battle arena to maintain sustainability in preparing PT KAI Talent to face the era of change

B. Recommendations:

- a. PT KAI Goes International through English Habits, and Work Abroad Opportunities for PT KAI's Top Talent.
- b. Transforming Service Quality and Security by maximizing the use of AI and Renewable Technology in all Business processes.
- c. Creating Synergies (Including SOEs) through harmonious and collaborative strategic alliances with other state-owned companies.
- d. Global Partnership as the best transportation ecosystem solution for Indonesia by opening up to the existence of a Global partnership business scheme
- e. Service and Leader form an actor known as Servant Leader. For further research, the researcher suggested research on the topic "How Servant Leaders, with Servant Leadership, Shape Culture, Digital Ecosystem, High Quality Service, and Organizational Capabilities so that PT KAI becomes a World Class Operator.

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APPENDIX

Variables	Dimension	No	Detailed Statements	Average Score	Beta	Category Score	Category Beta	Priority
Org. Cap	Speed	X5.1	Here we are able to respond to changes quickly and remain accountable with work	5,51	0,515	High Score	High Influence	1
	Speed	X5.2	Here we think creatively in solving problems as quickly as possible	5,50	0,515	High Score	High Influence	2
	Adaptable to change	X5.7	Here we are required to be able to adapt to the changing environment and work processes	5,49	0,515	High Score	High Influence	3
	Adaptable to change	X5.8	Here we are aware of changes in the work environment	5,41	0,515	High Score	High Influence	4
	Innovation	X5.4	Here the innovation program is one of our priorities	5,39	0,515	High Score	High Influence	5
	Efficiency	X5.15	Here we are instilled the value of efficiency as a motto in all business processes	5,39	0,515	High Score	High Influence	6
	Strategic Responsiveness	X5.10	Here we have a clear policy to deal with technological changes	5,38	0,515	High Score	High Influence	7

Innovation	X5.3	Here we are used to planning innovation programs in all process lines	5,36	0,515	High Score	High Influence	8
Efficiency	X5.16	Here we are able to do each other's work as efficiently as possible	5,36	0,515	High Score	High Influence	9
Customer Connectivity	X5.5	Here we maintain connectivity with the government as stakeholders	5,34	0,515	High Score	High Influence	10
Strategic Responsiveness	X5.9	Here we have a system that is able to provide strategic responses to external disturbances (disasters, pandemics, etc.)	5,33	0,515	High Score	High Influence	11
Ready to Strategic Alliance	X5.14	We believe that the partnership established by PT KAI today is strategic and very important	5,28	0,515	High Score	High Influence	12
Ready to Strategic Alliance	X5.13	We believe the international partnership strategy is right to anticipate the sustainability of PT KAI's business growth	5,24	0,515	High Score	High Influence	13
Customer Connectivity	X5.6	Here we are directed to maintain intimate relationships with customers	5,21	0,515	High Score	High Influence	14
Talent	X5.18	Our leaders can already be equated with world class railway company leaders	5,16	0,515	High Score	High Influence	15
Talent	X5.17	Here our competencies are all equivalent to Global railway companies human capital	5,13	0,515	High Score	High Influence	16
International Environment	X5.11	Here we all know world-class railway companies	4,77	0,515	Average Score	High Influence	17

International Environment	X5.12	Here almost all of us master English well	4,26	0,515	Low Score	High Influence	18
Responsiveness	X4.5	PT KAI employees are always responsive to serve customers	5,63	0,352	High Score	Average Influence	19
Responsiveness	X4.6	PT KAI responds quickly and accurately to customer complaints	5,57	0,352	High Score	Average Influence	20
Reliability	X4.3	We believe that PT KAI is reliable for transportation service users	5,53	0,352	High Score	Average Influence	21
Tangibles	X4.1	We believe that our products and services can be understood easily by PT KAI's customers	5,51	0,352	High Score	Average Influence	22
Reliability	X4.4	Trains in Indonesia are adequate for customers and well maintained	5,51	0,352	High Score	Average Influence	23
Empathy	X4.10	I am sure that PT KAI employees communicate clearly and are very helpful to customers	5,50	0,352	High Score	Average Influence	24
Assurance	X4.8	I believe PT KAI's operations (time and ease of access) are in line with customer expectations	5,49	0,352	High Score	Average Influence	25
Assurance	X4.7	Here we believe passengers in Indonesia prefer to use train services compared to other public transportation	5,47	0,352	High Score	Average Influence	26

Empathy	X4.9	PT KAI employees give individual attention to help customers	5,39	0,352	High Score	Average Influence	27
Tangibles	X4.2	We believe that our products and services are satisfactory to our customers	5,12	0,352	Average Score	Average Influence	28

Cite this Article: David Gamaliel, Yuni Ros Bangun (2023). Talent Readiness of PT KAI to Face the Era of Change. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 6(6), 3160-3178